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ESG Principles - Sustainable Finance Responsible investment and sustainability in the financial and capital markets

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CONCEPT

The acronym ESG stands as the abbreviation for “environmental, social and governance”, _ in English “environmental , social and governance ” (ESG) and relates to the set of practices that take into account environmental, social and governance factors, aiming at achieving sustainability goals.

It is now important to explain, in greater detail, the reflection of this acronym in business strategies.

Environmental (A)

The environmental issue has gained more relevance in recent years, there is no doubt that air pollution, rivers, seas, desertification and global warming are a reality and present a dilemma where companies can be part of the problem (high carbon emissions) or part of the solution.

From an environmental point of view, it is necessary to analyze how the company operates, whether it is committed to

the preservation and correct use of resources (energy consumption and energy efficiency), implementation of recycling and waste management policies and adoption of actions with a view to to minimize the environmental impacts of its operations.

“The life of companies that emit high levels of carbon in their processes will be increasingly difficult. Not only are consumers looking for companies that are more connected with environmental issues, but the costs of being a pollutant will only increase (costs, fees and taxes)”, comments Bartunek .

In this scenario, he states that aspects to be observed in companies’ environmental issues are: energy consumption, water and energy efficiency; recycling; emission of polluting gases (example: carbon emission); preservation of biodiversity; anti-disaster measures and environmental awareness.

Social (S)

Regarding social factors, what is

observed is the way in which the company manages relationships with its employees, suppliers, customers and the community. In this “S” pillar, the actions to eliminate gender pay disparities, equal opportunities, professional development (education) of employees and also the protection of local communities can be cited as examples.

Bartunek comments that “social” encompasses the company’s relationships with its employees, customers and community. The aspects to be observed in the social issues of companies are: engagement and staff turnover; intellectual development of employees; talent attraction and retention; employee health and safety; relations with customers; supplier network and impacts on the local community.

Governance (G)

Finally, in terms of governance, companies must pay attention to issues related to their leadership, their internal controls, executive compensation, audits and shareholder rights, which can be exemplified by the adoption of policies and practices (effective and assertive) anti-corruption and bribery, antitrust, as well as any action aimed at transparency and responsibility in the business carried out.

The topic refers, briefly, to how the relationships between shareholders and controllers are governed. According to Bartunek , the aspects to be observed in corporate governance issues are: alignment and shareholder rights; in executive compensation; independence, experience and remuneration of the Board of Directors; accounting practices; soundness of internal controls and processes; related party transactions; transparency and accountability; share class structure

and corruption prevention.

Obviously, the adoption of measures related to the practice of ESG will result in expenses for the companies. However, according to Francesco Rutibliani , in an article published on the Techedge website , such expenses should be seen as investments. “In fact, companies that have incorporated ESG into their strategies have reaped several benefits, including increased market confidence and shareholder value,” says Rubliani . For investors, companies’ adoption of ESG-related policies has become an indicator for analyzing a company’s performance and its role in society.

This set of best practices has been improving in the corporate world, an example of ESG practice being the creation of the Principles for Responsible Investments (PRI), developed at the initiative of the UN program for the environment (UNEP-FI) and the Global Compact of the UN to guide the market in the search for responsible development. The Principles for Responsible United Nations Investment (PRI) is an international organization that works to promote the incorporation of environmental, social and corporate governance (ESG) factors into investment decision making.

Launched in April 2006, the PRI had over 2,300 participating financial institutions as of January 2020. These institutions participate by becoming signatories to the PRI’s six key principles by regularly reporting on their progress.

Today, signatories to the United Nations Principles for Responsible Investment account for more than \$80 trillion in assets worldwide and include some of the world’s largest and most influential investors.

UNDERSTANDING THE UNITED

NATIONS PRINCIPLES FOR RESPONSIBLE INVESTMENT (PRI)

The organization's main idea is that when making an investment decision, environmental and social factors are taken into account and are shown to be preponderant in investors' choice of companies and funds. PRI supporters argue that it is financially and ethically irresponsible not to consider a company's environmental impact when evaluating its merits as an investment. As a way of guiding company behavior, the PRI presented six basic principles, with which signatory companies must agree to commit. As expressed on the organization's website, the six principles are as follows:

Principle 1: We will incorporate ESG issues into investment analysis and decision-making processes.

Principle 2: We will be active owners and incorporate ESG issues into our ownership policies and practices.

Principle 3: We will seek appropriate disclosure on ESG matters by the entities in which we invest.

Principle 4: We will promote the acceptance and implementation of the Principles in the investment industry.

Principle 5: We will work together to increase our effectiveness in implementing the Principles.

Principle 6: Each of us will report on our activities and progress in implementing the Principles.

Together, the companies that are signatories to these six principles are responsible for a total of assets under management of more than \$80 trillion.

ORIGIN

Practices related to ESG investments emerged in the 1960s, a period in which some investors began to eliminate companies from their portfolios based on environmental, social and governance criteria. In this scenario, companies that showed little environmental and social responsibility became less attractive.

Officially, ESG investments appeared on the market in January 2004, driven by the then Secretary-General of the United Nations, Kofi Annan. He sent letters to 50 directors of large companies to support the United Nations Global Compact.

Thus, the term ESG came from the publication of the report *Who Cares Wins*, Connecting Financial Markets to a Changing World, an initiative developed by the Global Compact, together with the World Bank in 2005, which aimed to raise awareness of the need to incorporate environmental, social and governance factors in capital markets, aiming to ensure more sustainable markets and better results for societies. Concurrently, the United Nations Environment Program Finance Initiative (UNEP/FI) produced the "Freshfield Report", which demonstrated the relevance of ESG issues to financial assessment.

Thus, with these two reports and with the initiative of investors from UNEP-FI and the UN Global Compact, the framework was formed for the launch of the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI)

REFLECTIONS OF THE ADOPTION OF THE SGA

For the community, there are numerous advantages of incorporating ESG criteria by companies, this represents an evolution in the management process. By directing resources to generate positive impacts from a

socio-environmental and governance perspective, an environment favorable to sustainability is created.

The adoption of ESG criteria in the main financial markets abroad is at an advanced stage, and this issue is a reality for most investors. In Brazil the subject has been debated for some time, however, the discussion is still in an embryonic stage. In January 2020, Larry Fink, president of BlackRock (one of the largest investment fund managers in the world), wrote a letter, addressed to the CEOs of the companies that receive investments from his company, placing sustainability as a strategic focus of investments and the future of companies.

Nowadays, a large part of society gives importance to companies aligned with their values when choosing where they will work, which products to consume, which brands they have more affinity with and in which companies they will invest. Care for the environment, people and transparency are some of the factors analyzed. Furthermore, with the large presence of social media, it would be difficult for a company to escape unscathed if, for example, it employed slave labor or caused an environmental disaster, thus destroying its reputation and therefore its market value.

Currently in Brazil, several managers are choosing companies to compose the portfolios of their investment funds, prioritizing those that have their management models aligned with the ESG criteria and, of course, with good growth prospects. Some of these brokerage firms have launched equity investment funds on the market exclusively composed of companies that are part of the IBOVESPA and that follow the ASG criteria. Managers such as SulAmerica Investimentos, Veritas Capital, JGP and Fama, among others,

are some of the examples. Some even allocate part or all of the fees charged from investors to social projects. In fact, there has been a demand for financial products that meet these requirements for some time on the part of many investors.

As society in general, fund managers and investors are increasingly concerned about the issue, with a large movement of companies to implement these ESG practices, believing that this is the path to success. However, the main difficulty is that it is not enough to want, it is necessary that there is a change in culture, values, purpose, with a long-term vision that cannot change with the change of the CEO, for example. Companies have to understand that this is the only way to perpetuate their business and that there is no dichotomy between profitability and ESG criteria. It is a constant and evolving process that, combined with good levels of governance, will ensure that companies that implement such practices are more profitable in the future.

Harvard professor Dr. Robert Eccles led research that generated a paper in 2012 titled "The Impact of Corporate Sustainability on Organizational Processes and Performance" which showed evidence that companies with high sustainability significantly outperform their competitors in the long term, both in terms of the valuation of their shares and in accounting performance.

It is essential for market operators to inform their associates about the importance of ESG companies that today are part of the decision criteria of most consumers, of the most diverse products and services on the market. The idea of "responsible capitalism" has fueled a coercion on companies to adopt and deliver high standards of

performance in environmental, social and governance issues, whose main pressure points can be observed in relations with investors, consumers and civil society.

Investor enforcement has emerged as a result of individuals increasingly concerned that their investments must not only be financially sound, but also sustainable and socially beneficial and ethical.

The importance given by investors in relation to AGS practices can be observed, for example, through the actions carried out by “B3 SA – Brasil, Bolsa, Balcão”, responsible for the Brazilian stock exchange, which developed the Corporate Sustainability Index (“ISE”) to measure the average performance of the shares of companies that are committed to adopting sustainable policies. The ISE currently comprises shares of 30 companies that add up to R\$1.64 trillion in market value. In a comparative analysis between the performance of equity funds classified as Sustainable and Responsible Investment (“ISR”) and the performance of the Ibovespa, it is observed that the former presented a higher accumulated financial return in the last six years, including in the crisis period, which proves that investors are increasingly aware of the sustainable and responsible management of companies.

When dealing with consumer pressure, the change in their behavior must be observed, which in addition to demanding a quality product and/or service, began to question the social and environmental role of the companies from which they consume. Risks to companies’ reputation have increased with increasingly vigilant consumers, which forces them to also adjust the way they position themselves on ESG issues and practices.

Any type of practice that demonstrates a lack of responsibility with environmental and/or social issues is no longer considered acceptable, the negative impacts are immediate and extremely harmful to the companies’ reputation. Along with consumers, there are institutions of society that promote, by various means, campaigns denouncing the absence and/or failure of responsible conduct, whose reputational risks are immeasurable.

Likewise, responsible actions that create a positive impact on society are immediately recognized and applauded, becoming a model of corporate conduct to be expanded and copied. This is the case, for example, of what happened with the trainee program for leadership positions, exclusively for blacks, promoted by the company Magazine Luiza. Despite some criticisms, in our mistaken view, this measure was very well received and undoubtedly demonstrates the possibility of a corporation to contribute socially and positively, by promoting the inclusion of blacks in leadership positions, historically held by whites, and which is even aligned with the GT Technical Note on Race No. 001/2018, from the Public Labor Ministry.

It remains clear, therefore, that it is essential that companies start to integrate ESG issues in their management, if they want to remain attractive to investors, as well as to the general public.

REGULATION ON THE THEME

It is evident that, given the novelty of the subject in Brazil, that there is still an incipient regulation, with no explicit penalty from a legal point of view in what relates to non-compliance with such principles, which in itself imposes a legal challenge, as companies are

adapting to the implementation and compliance of the ESG regulations, which will necessarily lead to a review of the current regulatory norms.

So far, there is no legal rule that presents the 3 pillars of the AGS (environmental, social and governance) in a unified and specific way. However, it is possible to say that, both in Brazil and in the world, there are already general rules that allow and encourage companies to analyze these criteria in their operations and decision making.

In Brazil, for example, the provisions of the Corporate Law (Law nº 6.404/1976) can be interpreted in order to understand that companies must observe ESG factors in the decision-making process, by requiring in its article 116, sole § [4], that the controlling shareholder use its power of control to make the company realize its object and fulfill its social function. The State-Owned Companies Law (Law nº 13.303/2016), through its article 8, item IX, obliges public companies and mixed capital companies to prepare sustainability reports or integrated reports.

Within the scope of the financial system, Brazilian legislation is complemented by rules of the National Monetary Council ("CMN"), such as, for example, CMN Resolution No. resulted in the publication of the "Previc Guide to Best Investment Practices", which has as a novelty the introduction of a specific section to address ESG guidelines in investment management.

On environmental issues, Brazilian legislation has been incorporating international commitments, such as Law No. 12,187/09, which establishes the National Policy on Climate Change, and Law No.).

As market regulatory agents are

dynamic bodies such as AMBIMA, an independent and self-regulating element that operates in the financial market, launched in 2020 a guide for incorporating ESG aspects into investment analysis for banks and brokerages.

We also have the Central Bank of Brazil (BACEN), which also seeking to embrace the subject, launched its ASG agenda in 2020, thus being aligned with other Central Banks. In this agenda, aiming to guide the financial market, BACEN includes climate risk scenarios, seeking to develop a financial line of sustainable liquidity.

Last but not least, we have the National Bank for Economic and Social Development (BNDES), which recently created a line of financing, through the so-called BNDES Credit ASG, with free destination, where the primary requirement is that the company improve your sustainability indicators.

In principle, BNDES Credit ASG will be allocated to companies in specific segments: the wood chain focused on reforestation, manufacturers of equipment for the renewable energy and energy efficiency chain, mining, steel. These four sectors have great potential for improvement in environmental terms. The fifth sector, which has a greater potential for social than environmental impact, is that of small internet providers. Increasing connectivity is one of the goals of the BNDES' Triennial Plan 2020 -2022.

In the international scenario, the "Modern Slavery Act" of the United Kingdom, which aims for companies to take steps to ensure that slavery and human trafficking do not occur in their supply chains. Under this standard, companies with a global turnover of £36 million and operating in the United

Kingdom must publish a statement for each financial year, which must contain measures taken to ensure that slavery and human trafficking are not occur in the company or in the supply chain.

However, despite the existence of the aforementioned standards, in addition to others that deal in an isolated way with the pillars of the AGS, it must be recognized that we are still facing a timid regulatory environment, with informal and non-binding standards, and it is certain that such standards, mainly in line with public opinion, are guiding the way in which ESG integration is carried out by companies.

CONCLUSION

Today, in the corporate world, there is no possibility of rejecting or ignoring the application of ESG principles, compliance with its issues is something that cannot be ignored by companies. To attract investments and customers, engagement with the theme will be necessary and this will directly influence how companies will be seen by the market.

As explained, practice shows that there is still no rigid and binding standard to integrate ESG factors in the management of companies, and this integration is generally conducted by a set of good practices and principles that serve as a guide, and it is up to the manager /investor adapt them to their reality and needs.

However, even in an embryonic regulatory environment, failure to meet expectations related to ESG practices will result in legal challenges, as corporations will be exposed to various obligations, such as: reporting on ESG practices, reinterpretation of existing regulatory duties, as well as any need to present a defense in court, due to litigation based, for example,

on negligence in relation to its socio-environmental responsibilities.

In this way, the ESG purpose is to achieve commercial growth, also promoting sustainability, attention to society and good governance in companies. Therefore, the business adopts some measures to help and enhance these measures.

Considering the practical issue in the business environment, those who act according to ESG criteria and standards will be guided by these standards in decision-making and company policies. Thus, ethical values, social inclusion initiatives, ways of protecting and restructuring the environment, etc. can be adopted.

Some more skeptical and resistant may say that ESG is more a fad in the science of Management, but what no one can ignore is the fact that its emergence takes place from financial market initiatives, more specifically by banks and investment funds. able to allocate huge amounts to companies aligned with best practices in their management and means of production. It is a trend with real chances of lasting, as it aligns the interests of consumers, who favor companies with socio-environmental responsibility and investors who, in addition to being concerned with the image they pass on by investing in committed companies, manage to obtain a better positioning in the market and, consequently, a better return on capital invested, the same is true for companies.

In view of all this, increasingly, the adoption of ESG/ESG criteria has been providing sustainable benefits to companies' businesses, such as: brand appreciation, reputation improvement, risk reduction, talent attraction and the conquest of new

markets. These criteria, when adopted, reveal the sustainability of the business, indicate the solidity, transparency, and quality of the companies' performance, providing greater security for investors and consumers, who wish to contribute resources and establish commercial relationships with the enterprises.

Investment (PRI), 2019. Available at: [https://www.unpri.org/download?ac=10969#:~:text=Os%20Princ%C3%ADpios%20para%20o%20Investimento%20Responses%C3%A1vel%20\(PRI\)%20were%20created%20by,for%20as%20pr%C3%A1tica%20from%20investment](https://www.unpri.org/download?ac=10969#:~:text=Os%20Princ%C3%ADpios%20para%20o%20Investimento%20Responses%C3%A1vel%20(PRI)%20were%20created%20by,for%20as%20pr%C3%A1tica%20from%20investment)

REFERENCES

<https://www.capitalreset.com/guilherme-benchimol-da-xp-empresa-que-nao-for-esg-vai-acabar/>

<https://www.famainvestimentos.com.br/artigorevistaie>

<https://exame.com/blog/florian-bartunek/ambiental-social-e-governanca-asg-voce-ja-esta-atrasado/>

<https://www.techedgegroup.com/pt/blog/questoes-ambientais-sociais-e-de-governan%C3%A7a-quem-se-importa-ganha-por-que-a-asg-importante-no-business-world>

<https://estrategiasocial.com.br/criterios-asg-mais-um-modismo/>

BM&FBOVESPA, The Value of the ISE – Major Studies and Investor Perspectives, November 2012. Available at: <http://www.b3.com.br/data/files/86/77/A4/93/684135103A135D25790D8AA8/O-ISE-A4/93/684135103A135D25790D8AA8/O-ISE-Value.pdf> .
[A4/93/684135103A135D25790D8AA8/O-ISE-Value.pdf](http://www.b3.com.br/data/files/86/77/A4/93/684135103A135D25790D8AA8/O-ISE-A4/93/684135103A135D25790D8AA8/O-ISE-Value.pdf) .

Anbima , ESG Guide – Incorporation of ESG Aspects into Investment Analysis, January 2020. Available at: <https://www.anbima.com.br/data/files/1A/50/EE/31/BFDEF610CA9C4DF69B2BA2A8/ANBIMA-ASG-Guide-2019.pdf>

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